

SOCIAL SCIENCES

A SCIENTIFIC-CONCEPTUAL APPROACH TO THE NATIONAL SECURITY PROBLEM: FORMATION OF NATIONAL SECURITY SYSTEM IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the concept of national security, which is of actual importance in modern times, has been widely researched and comprehensively studied. The collapse of the former USSR caused a change in the geopolitical and military-geostrategic situation of the world. As in the newly independent states, the Azerbaijani state has set itself the main task of creating a national development and national security strategy. In the article, it is mentioned that certain material and moral conditions of national security system of Azerbaijan were formed in the former Soviet period, and mainly the period of independence was involved in the research. Not only the security of the state, but also the security of the individual and the society, and the protection of national interests in all fields are explained here.

Keywords: national security, threat, national interest, international security, state policy, political independence, South Caucasus, military doctrine.

INTRODUCTION:

National security of the state is a part of its national interests. Azerbaijan's national security means protecting the country, its citizens and its territory from various dangers and threats, as well as ensuring Azerbaijan's long-term development potential. The main figure in the formation of national security policy in Azerbaijan is the Commander-in-Chief- the President, to whom all law enforcement agencies and armed forces are subordinated with the support of the Security Council, a special advisory body. It is the President who defines the political course in this field, makes the main decisions and approves the conceptual documents (primarily the national security strategy) compiled by the Security Council. Only the president can declare a state of emergency or martial law or impose economic sanctions on other countries. An important component of Azerbaijan's national security is its military security. In the current Military Doctrine of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the state of protection of the vital interests of a person, society and the state from external and internal military threats is defined as the absence of a military threat, or military force or the threat of its use characterized by the ability to resist it. Since the topic is always relevant, there is always a special need to conduct research on it.

II. Historical aspects of national security issues

It should be noted that the first comprehensive study of threat and security was published by Kenneth Waltz in 1954 under the title "Man, The State and War". By analyzing the views of classical philosophers on war, the author determines that there are two main ideas in Western philosophy:

First, it is possible to reduce the conflicts that lead to wars;

Second, it is possible to eliminate conflicts that lead to wars.

Both determinations led the author to answer the fundamental question, such as "whether war is a part of human nature" [41.p.63].

This question brought back the controversial issue that arose in the understanding of European politics in the 17th century in the form of "man as a dangerous creature" again.

The idea that "man is a dangerous being" was created as a result of the theories formed by biological research in Europe in the 17th century. In particular, the philosophical debates started by T.Hobbes and I.Kant about "the good and the bad of human nature" constitute the historical background of the concept of "national security" in the 19th century. These disputes arose at the core in parallel with Christianity's replacement of teachings on religious and moral education of the metaphor of "peace and violence" in human nature by rational-deterministic concepts.

Although the term "national" in the concept of "national security" began to be used in the political sphere in the 19th century, the term "security" entered European politics with the Peace of Westphalia in 1648. This peace is accepted the initial stage in the formation of the modern European concept [27.p.356].

The Peace of Westphalia that ended the Thirty Years' War in Europe, included peace treaties signed on May 15 and October 24, 1648, in Osnabrück and Münster, with the participation of 275 representatives from the Catholic kingdoms and Protestant kingdoms. The treaty also ended the Eighty Years' War between Spain and the Dutch Republic. The main feature of this agreement is that the European states made the transition from "the right of divine representation to the right of mutual competition". This also revealed the "concept of sovereign states" in Europe [12.p.40].

In interstate relations in Europe, the principle of divine justice and the state of God (the right of succession to the Holy Roman Empire) was replaced by an economic concept of "competitive relations" [21.p.637].

With the Peace of Westphalia, the political powers in the European system of interstate relations protected economic relations, on the one hand and became the

guarantor of commercial relations at the legal level, on the other hand. While Westphalia was considered the first attempt to pave the way for the concept of international relations, it also gave a new meaning to the concept of security. Although the Peace of Westphalia was entitled "The majesty of God and the Security of Christianity" in accordance with the traditional legal language of Europe, it proclaimed "one global, eternal, true and sincere Christian peace and friendship" [24.p.36-37].

With this agreement, while the concept of "Christendom" was replaced by the concept of "Europe", empires, dynasties and religious authority, which were the political-religious foundations of Christendom, were replaced by states. Thus, the states appeared on the stage as the main actors of the international system from the Peace of Westphalia in 1648. Security began to become the basic principle when the state set the secular standards of political-legal relations. The states trying to protect their own security also had the mission of protecting the legal, political and economic relations between each other. This led to the emergence of the concept of security and the issue of security in European political thought [4.p.71].

The issues of "legitimacy of the ruler" put forward by Machiavelli became the problem of "legitimacy of state power" in the works of T. Hobbes, I. Kant and J. J. Rousseau in the 17th century. Within the framework of this problem, Kant came up with the thesis of "creation of eternal peace", while Hobbes and Rousseau described it as "the struggle of powers that constantly benefit states from each other". Therefore, the task of the states was to balance the power of the other in order not to allow one to prevail over the other [9.p.207-220].

Security, which occupies an important place in the Western philosophical thought and the concept of law, paved the way for concepts such as "power", "power relations", "movement", and "profit" to become a subject of controversy. These terms led to the formation of concepts about security issues by currents such as idealism, realism, liberalism and Marxism that emerged in the 19th century [6.p.150].

The literal meaning of security, which is the equivalent of the Latin word "securus" in the form of English "security", is "tranquility". "Se" in the word "se-cura" means "free from" in Latin, that is, "to be sure of something, to be comfortable and free." As a term used in European political thought since 1432, security began to acquire a secular essence from the seventeenth century [15.p.1722].

As a term, *security* is the opposite of threat and danger, and means *freedom from fear*. At the same time, this word implies the realization of necessary conditions for ensuring security (*freedom from wants*). In other words, security means tranquility on the one hand, and preservation of the continuity of tranquility on the other hand [23.p.90-92].

The perception of security as a term denoting "freedom" was directly related to the last two of his four statements in the form of a) freedom of speech, b) freedom of belief, c) comfort in meeting needs, d) being comfortable in the face of fears, voiced by US President

F. Roosevelt in the Atlantic agreement announcing the establishment of the United Nations [45].

The concept of "national security" in international relations caused extensive discussions together with the "*National Security Act*" adopted by the Congress on October 18, 1947 during the time of US President Henry S. Truman. The main aspect of this law is that national security was pronounced as a term more about politics [43.p.482].

However, the approach of the United States to the concept of national security was liberal in nature. It is interesting that the liberal view in explaining the concept of national security reflects the position of US federalism [33.p.236].

To be honest, the concept of security was first introduced into the political agenda by an idealistic philosophy. In other words, there are also idealist, realist and Marxist approaches in the concept of national security, unlike liberalism. Today's states defend this concept from the prism of those ideologies, which in turn causes serious problems between states in matters of national security.

III. A scientific-theoretical approach to the problem of national security

For the first time, the concept of security as a political normative and ontological principle was reflected in the works of "The Republic" by Plato and "Politics" by Aristotle. Socrates, the source of the ideas of both philosophers, actually revealed a realistic approach far from idealism by saying that "what is ideal for life is determined by the one who holds the power" [3.p.3].

Analyzing his philosophical ideas about what the "state" (*politica*) is, Plato presents security as an order [36.p.5].

When talking about "the union of the rulers and the ruled" in his work "*Politics*", Aristotle refers to the fact that the main purpose of their union is "the guarantee of security"[2.p.10].

The security was analyzed from a theological point of view in approaches of Plato who gives the soul (*doxa*) prominence and Aristotle who brings the mind (*logos*) to the forefront. As they approach the issue from a theological point of view, for Plato and Aristotle, who were looking for an answer to the question "why?", security was not a goal, but a need"[10.p.918].

Since the principles of divine justice and order occupied a central place in Christian theology, theologians and ideologists who approached the issue from the perspective of the "state of God" perceived the world as a dangerous place because they were based on formal principles [8.p.401-409].

Although Muslim political scientists and philosophers paid attention to the Plato-Aristotle approach, they recognized security as a fundamental principle of the state. According to Mavardi (11th century), one of the authors of the first "Policy" work in the Muslim world, morality and politics are inseparable. While one is the internal guarantee of human and state security, the other, namely politics, is the guarantee of its external security [30.p.28-106].

Although Farabi, Nizam al-Mulk and Ibn Khaldun have the same view on the issue, Ibn Khaldun analyzes

the issue in a broader perspective and provides historical and sociological explanations. According to Ibn Khaldun, who for the first time highlighted social life, sociality is the main necessity of human security [20.p.79-82].

Security first became a main area of the system of international relations with the Treaty of Westphalia in 1648. By understanding this concept within the framework of the "world order", I.Wallerstein points out that the concept of Europe created on the basis of security forms the concept of international politics. The "world system" envisaged by him has been formed in Europe since the 16th century, and has acquired an international essence by encompassing other cultures together with the colonial policy. [42.p.44].

The theory based on Machiavelli's concept played a starting role in the transformation of security into a leading concept in the system of international relations in Europe. When Machiavelli analyzed the concept of rulership based on real values, especially power, ambition and profit, he pointed out the ruler as the guarantor of the security of the geographical area he controlled. According to Machiavelli, who desired a political model based on state-centered and power principles, the protection of territory required the preservation of legal principles and relations since land had already become a fixed value. Therefore, the path to security goes through having a strong defense and an authoritarian administration [35.p.64].

When Machiavelli dreamed of a ruler-army-based system of government, he paved the way for the concept of a realistic state in the European understanding of politics. Jean Bodin (1530-1596) brought up a state-centered realist concept of security shortly after that. Formalizing politics around power, Bodin literally paved the way to the concept of "national power". According to Bodin, who formed the state on the basis of ruler and citizen, the basic condition of the state is its right to rule. The guarantee of the right to power was the basis of real security at the same time [1.p.64-74].

Since Bodin imagined the legal source of power on realistic grounds, he considered indivisibility and continuity as a condition. From Bodin onwards, the state and its continuity came to the fore, while the ruler was relegated to the second place in Western thought. The state model that he named "*respublica*" was the only dominant power and also the source of authority. Thus, the state itself became its own cause and source [7.p.15].

The views of Machiavelli and Bodin, the statements of Francis de Vitoria (1480-1546) and Franciscus Suarez (1568-1617) cut off the ties of the state, political power, and most importantly, human security with God, and based it on law within the framework of nature and on the basis of natural rules. Together with Hobbes, all bonds of power with the divine existence were cut off and an abstract and artificial state model was formed. As he perceived the state as a kind of automaton or machine, he was in search of a model perfected by the order of nature, The state, which is the source of itself, creates its own laws and becomes the guarantor of the security of both itself and its people at

the same time. Under the title of "On the Causes, Creation, and Definition of a State" in his work "Leviathan," Hobbes places the "security of the individual" in the initial stage: "The cause, purpose and objective of the restrictions that men who naturally like liberty and dominion over others when living in the case of states, subject themselves to protect themselves and thus live a happier life and ... it is about saving people from wars that are the inevitable result of their natural feelings" [19.p.127].

Hobbes's approach to the issue also revealed the liberal nature of security. Thus, a number of thinkers who came after him began to perceive security along with the concept of freedom. John Locke (1632-1704), Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) and John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) focused on a liberal concept of security. In the matter of freedom, the liberals who emphasized the realistic values of human nature approached the realists politically and the idealists from the point of view of the human ideal. But liberals, unlike realists and idealists, were not interested in changing human nature, but only in managing it. The liberals, divided into many branches of human freedom such as political, cultural, economic, social, conservative, and neoliberal, considered security worldwide [26.p.101].

The concept of liberal security was expressed as a fundamental thesis of critical philosophy in Immanuel Kant's (1724-1804) work "Eternal Peace". While accepting the global values of the Enlightenment, Kant emphasizes that by accepting wars as illegal and illegitimate, a republican government has the mission of regulating the equal and free relations of all citizens to ensure eternal peace. In his work "Eternal Peace", Kant, who dreamed of a federation of free and independent states as a kind of "United Nations Organization", expressed the need to eliminate the concept of war once and for all in order to ensure security [22.p.22-26].

Fichte (1762-1814), a follower of Kant, drew attention to the existence of world economic relations for the emergence of the concept of world law. According to Fichte, the fundamental property of a man is his own existence. Thus, in idealistic liberalism, security taken as the core human existence and value, and the sharing of this human value by all people, led them to unite in a secular order, legal platform and economic relations [14.p.308].

While preparing the dialectical plan of this concept, Hegel expressed that the basic desire that led people to this was "historical mind". In this sense, Hegel formulated the history of humanity on the basis of two foundations:

a)progress b)development [18.p.155-172].

Since these two foundations were achieved simply by European culture, the Western natural mind had the power to ensure the common values of humanity in an order and legal plane. And this is the expression of the concept of "security" which Europe has continued since 1648.

Influenced by Hegel's dialectical philosophy of history, Karl Marx (1818-1883) and Ludwig Feuerbach (1804-1872) analyzed the concept of materialist politics and economy mainly in the class consciousness of security and human identity from a materialist position

rejecting idealism, drawing attention to the commonality of "proletariat" problems in the world. According to Marx, who emphasized that capitalist property serves the concept of "modern slavery", the main value for people is labor. The safe sharing of human labor does not require government or money. Because these two create a constant crisis and dangerous situation by maintaining the power of the ruling class over the one that produces labor [16.p.78].

According to Marx, who pointed out the state carrying imperialist tendencies, it is precisely these tendencies that cause wars. Thus, Marx revealed the origin of the concept of war, which was expressed by Kant and threatened man.

Continuing the Marxist tradition, Michael Hardt and Antonino Negri sharply criticize Keynes's "theory of the capitalist state" in their joint work on the "critique of the concept of the state". They evaluate the concept of "capitalist reconstruction and welfare state" voiced by the United States, which acted on the claim of "national security" in the crisis of 1929, as "a new strategy, but an old tactic" [17.p.76-86].

Hardt and Negri's critique focuses on the security of capital and a clandestine attitude toward emerging threats to the Wilsonian values of the United States. This contrast of the United States, which defended national security as state policy and world policy, was caused by the contrast between the political strategy of Theodore Roosevelt and Woodrow Wilson. At the same time, this contrast arose from the way in which US foreign policy would choose between isolationist and international peace trends at the beginning of the 20th century. At the same time, this raised the question of the understanding that the United States should give to international world politics on the eve of "the gradual collapse of the international system centered on Europe and becoming America the center of global policy." This strategy, chosen by the United States against the background of becoming the center of world politics, was decisive for the rise of the concept of "national security" to the international level.

According to H.Kissinger, the basis of the mission policy that prompted America to "change the world" was that "the security dilemma that caused heartache and suffering in European countries did not concern America for almost one hundred and fifty years". "When it came to America, he participated twice in the world wars started by European nations. In each of these cases, the principle of the balance of forces was no longer effective at the moment when America was involved in the war and a paradoxical situation arose: it was the same balance of power that most Americans rejected with displeasure, but which, according to original thinking, has kept Americans safe until now and it was this imbalance that dragged America into the sphere of international politics" [25.p.26].

Robert Tosek and David Hendrikson argued that since the beginning of America, "states seem to reject the means they resort to in order to maintain their security and expand their ambitions, and at the same time are reluctant to reject the ambitions that necessitate the use of those means" [39.p.141].

The failure of Roosevelt's adjustment of American policy to the European equilibrium system was the loss of effectiveness of Europe's outdated competitive policy of world security. In the face of the inability of Europe," the homeland of state-nation, sovereignty and balance of forces," to maintain the international system, Wilson's principles put forward the concept of universal peace. America's mission should have been to guard that peace. America should have played a benevolent role for the world, according to Roosevelt, who argued that the task of making his influence felt on a global level belongs to America. In this sense, American presidents have not seen the role of the United States in the world within the framework of national interests, but have analyzed national interests together with the ratio of power. [37.p.29-30].

It turns out that the United States saw security not on the basis of the principle of balances, but in the construction of world peace according to the ratio of powers. This approach, as expressed by H.Kissinger, will consider the United States' system of nations a success in the aftermath of World War II, adopt world peace as an international political strategy, and in the continuation will give the United States the right to control the world. The formation and perception of the concept of national security in the present sense was due precisely to the new international conditions that arose after the Second World War. Exactly from that date the term national security entered the literature of international relations [29.p.2].

National security, which was formed during the Cold War years depending on the parameters and realistic approaches of the time, was considered mainly on two foundations:

- a) political independence linked to values that are important to protect
- b) territorial integrity [5.p.13].

IV. New approaches to the problem of national security and its modern nature

The concept of national security, how a state perceives threats directed against it in order to continue its existence, began to change after 1990, with the dissolution of the former USSR. From this time, national security, which did not have a specific meaning, began to be explained in a more diverse nature, gaining meaning and expression in accordance with the values of each country and power. Starting from this date, while the military nature of the term national security was exaggerated, it began to take on a generalized essence in matters that take over the world agenda in emergency situations (such as terrorism). With a more substantial wording, national security began to be pronounced in the form of self-defense of a country against internal and external threats. In a more general and broad sense, national security was perceived in the way of understanding all kinds of measures taken in order to protect the state order within the framework of the concept of national security. In this sense, national security has essentially become a term that makes it important that:

1. The ability of a state to maintain its political independence and right to free decision-making through the armed forces, diplomacy and intelligence network;

2. To act together in terms of world security against common problems (terrorism, climate, chemical, nuclear weapons, etc.) at the international level. [38.p.16].

This gives reason to say that the concept of security is divided into two, objective and subjective, and its criteria have a pronounced essence in a scientific sense. In other words, security "with its essence reflecting intellectual labor, philosophy of life, expressed the composition and means of service, depending on who formed the power holders, balance and sharing ideologically, depending on who owns it" [11.p.159].

According to Kissinger, with the Vienna conference in 1815, the process of "interconnection of peoples" began in foreign policy, and thus the term "international relations" arose. However, when the concept of what is important for countries" in foreign policy when the balance between values and necessities is established" began to come to the fore, the idea of peace, which is more important for the world, began to differ in accordance with the interests of countries and national security concerns. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, there were objective conditions for thinking of a new and common form of security. The terrorist attack in the United States, which occurred in 2001, showed that world peace is more important than the interests of national States and security concerns. However, due to the underestimation of this process by the United States, in the first decade of the XXI century, a number of world states have forced them to reconsider and evaluate their national security concepts. The national security documents approved by the United States in 2006 and 2010, the United Kingdom in 2008 and 2010, France in 2008 and 2013, Russia in 2000 and 2009, and China in 2011 and 2015 revealed the importance of national security concerns for states rather than world peace, as Kissinger claimed [44.p.13-22].

It is noteworthy that the security concerns of states regarding politics and war are also accepted and shared by citizens. [31.p.344].

Ultimately, security is a concept that ensures that peoples, citizens and individuals are not harmed in various activities as much as states. In this case, ensuring security is a public need. Security, therefore, has a social meaning, such as law and order. The elements that constitute a threat to the life of a state, society and individual have meaning and essence in relation to security. This objective and subjective nature of security is also marked by the expansion and narrowing of its boundaries. According to Arnold Wolfers, any threat to the truth about the value desired to be acquired or protected refers to objective security, the emergence of a fear and concern about those values desired to be protected denotes subjective security [43.p.501].

Undoubtedly, the fact that the most notable term about security is profit indicates that profit relations are also effective in the concept of national security. As among states, among peoples and individuals, the relevance of the profit factor, the idea that everything included in the concept of security is useful or harmful is emphasized. Therefore, the facts that are often voiced about security also play a key role for profit relations.

In this sense, for Richard Ulman, security is considered a goal as well as an outcome [40.p.133].

From the debates "about the nature of security" started by Wolfers in 1952, a large number of statements and explanations of security have emerged to this day. The Peace of Westphalia in 1648 in political relations, the Vienna Conference in 1815 in international relations, the security that emerged in the United States with Wilson's principles in state strategy, acquired a national character after World War II and became the defining term in interstate relations.

In all cases, security has been a theoretical concept, applied from theory to practical life, especially to practical politics. What is dangerous for the state is becoming a profit for other states, just as it can be safe for citizens. Therefore, in matters related to security, a number of politicians, especially lawyers, consider the accepted international treaties and agreements as the basis. That is, the concept of national security is obliged to be regulated by international legal norms. Although the concept of perceiving the world as a legal whole has manifested itself as a platform in the international arena, it has not been fully reflected in practice [13.p.283].

Because in many cases, relations regarding law are being changed and threatened with national security as the main reason. In this case, "rule of law" and "rules of security" remain undefined as the main problem for the world.

As a subject of international relations, the reputation and image of each state in the world is directly related to its national security policy. National security policy acts as one of the main indicators of the country's internal issues, such as socio-political, economic and spiritual development of the country, resistance to threats emanating from the external world, internal stability of effective public administration, unification of citizens around national ideas, goals, practices, participation in socio-political life, etc. It should be borne in mind that the security system is created by each state itself to ensure its national interests. It should be noted that certain material and moral conditions of the national security system of Azerbaijan were formed during the former Soviet era. There is also rich international experience in this field. In the period of independence, this problem is of a more complex nature. If the national security of Azerbaijan was adapted to the administrative-command system in the former Soviet period, in the period of independence, it implies the security of not only the state, but also the individual and the society, and the protection of national interests in all areas.

As a result of the collapse of the former USSR, the change in the geopolitical and military-geostrategic situation of the world, the transition of new independent states from one political system to another and other transnational processes put forward the task of creating a national development and national security strategy for the Azerbaijani state, as in all post-Soviet republics. In the first years of its independence, the justified approaches and perceptions in the state institutions and society regarding the essence, main directions, ways

and mechanisms of implementation of Azerbaijan's national development and security policy were quite superficial. However very soon, under the leadership of national leader Heydar Aliyev, a new concept of national security was created, reflecting independent state interests and international values, general security norms and national postulates, and containing the main tasks, directions and priorities of the security of the individual, society and the state, and in the subsequent period, it was improved by passing through various stages of development. The theoretical bases and principles of the national security policy are stable or changeable depending on the general situation of the state and society, the level of development, are renewed and improved according to the national needs and associated with the solution of the main state tasks. The formation of a single national idea-Azerbaijanism and raising it to the level of state policy was of great importance in ensuring the national security of Azerbaijan and in determining the essence, main tasks, and directions of the policy pursued in this area.

V. National security system of Azerbaijan and its sources

The main source of the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on National Security, the National Security Concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Military Doctrine of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main principles and outlines of the national security system were clearly expressed in a number of reports and speeches of national leader Heydar Aliyev, including his speeches on the establishment and activities of the National Security Council of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The forces and other state bodies that interact on the basis of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan and are responsible for ensuring national security within the scope of their powers organize the system of ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan and are responsible for ensuring national security. The system of ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan is created for the development of a unified state policy, effective implementation of the process of protecting national interests in social, political, economic, military, information, environmental, scientific, cultural and moral, as well as other fields, in the form of complex activities. Ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan has the following objectives: human security - the availability of favorable conditions for all-round human development, implementation of state measures in the field of protection of human rights and freedoms; society's security- protection of the vital interests and needs of the Azerbaijani people, as well as the system of social values from threats; state security - protection of the independence, sovereignty, territorial integrity, constitutional structure and other vital interests of the Republic of Azerbaijan from threats. Ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan involves the following main tasks: detection, analysis and prediction of threats to the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan; preparation and implementation of measures to prevent threats to the national security of

the Republic of Azerbaijan; the formation and training of forces and means that ensure the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan; in case of direct threats and conspiracies to the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan, mobilization of all forces and means, implementation of a set of appropriate countermeasures, localization and elimination of possible consequences of the situation; participation in the provision of general and regional security in accordance with the international obligations of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In the current conditions, the Azerbaijani society is going through a very important stage of building its own security system and the successful solution of the typical problems of this stage requires reliable scientific and informational support of our national security, the organization of high professional and moral-psychological training of the personnel engaged in this system, determination of ways and means leading to the strengthening of the patriotism and national self-consciousness of citizens, especially the young generation and the rules of their effective use. As it is known from the world experience, the main means of solving all these issues is the development and adoption of the concept of national security and the implementation of the domestic and foreign policy based on it. Therefore, the issues related to the solution of this task, first of all scientific-theoretical problems, are as complex as they are actual and relevant. Modern Azerbaijani society, especially the institutions that should ensure its national security, are constantly monitoring threats that undermine national security, constantly working on improving the ways and means of preventing them, increasing their efficiency. Among the means of solving these tasks, the basic role is played by the constitution of the state. It is on the basis of the constitution that the law on national security of the state is developed.

The signing of the oil contract called "Contract of the century" by national leader Heydar Aliyev on September 20, 1994 not only increased the economic power of our country, but also became a serious political factor of the national security of our republic. This agreement drew the attention of the international community not only to the Azerbaijani oil, but also to the socio-political processes taking place in Azerbaijan. Based on this necessity, the Law on National Security of the Republic of Azerbaijan entered into force by the order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated June 29, 2004 (*No. 712-IIQ*). In the second article of the law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On National Security", "the state, people and society are specified as the objects of national security. All three of these facilities are an integral part of the national security system" [28].

By the Order of the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated May 23, 2007, the approval of the national security concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan was a step arising from historical necessity. "The National Security Concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan is a set of goals, principles and approaches of policies and measures aimed at protecting the personality, society and the state from external and internal threats in the Republic of Azerbaijan by emphasizing the inde-

pendence, territorial integrity and democratic development path of the state, its integration into the Euro-Atlantic space as a strategic choice, as well as the diversity of its balanced foreign policy" [34].

The Republic of Azerbaijan also takes appropriate measures to prevent activities threatening national security and damaging national interests. In this sense, the approval of the "Military Doctrine of the Republic of Azerbaijan" by the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan on June 8, 2010 was a step arising from historical necessity. As a part of the strategy of ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan founded by Heydar Aliyev, the military doctrine is a document defining the conceptual basis of the military security system aimed at protecting the rights and interests of a person, society and the state from internal and external, military and other threats. At the same time, this doctrine reflects the position of the Republic of Azerbaijan on issues related to timely detection, analysis, assessment, prevention of threats to military security, provision of adequate resistance to them, preparation of the state, population and territory for defense, the creation of an effective military security system, prevention of war and armed conflicts, suppression armed aggression. The legal basis of this doctrine is the Constitution, Laws and other normative legal acts of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the concept of national security, and other conceptual documents in the field of national security. Also, "Military doctrine" is an open document for revision, clarification and additions, taking into account the constantly dynamics of the security environment of the Republic of Azerbaijan [32].

Conclusion

As a result, it should be noted that one of the main goals of the national security policy of Azerbaijan is the Armenia-Azerbaijan, Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, which lasted about 30 years as a result of the aggressive policy of Armenia, and Azerbaijan achieved its territorial integrity with the signing of the act of capitulation by Armenia in the second Karabakh war lasting 44 days. The settlement of the conflict not only paved the way for national development and security of Azerbaijan, but also had a significant impact on the socio-economic development of the entire region and the further strengthening of peace and security in the region and the world.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan, represented by its national interests in the context of regional security, Azerbaijan acts as one of the important geopolitical, geo-economic and military-geostrategic spaces not only of the South Caucasus, the Caspian-Black Sea basin, but also of Eurasia and the global world as a whole with its geopolitical spatial characteristics, economic, political and legal presence. In accordance with international practice, for the same purpose, the National Security Council, National Army, State Security Service and its relevant bodies, as well as educational and scientific-research institutions for scientific-information and personnel support of all these have been established in Azerbaijan.

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